

Testing non-linearity and saturation of a RF current probe

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Abstract—The behavior of RF current probes in simulated real usage conditions is considered, for what regards non-linearity and saturation in presence of large mains current intensity. A setup is described that allows the testing of variable bias conditions with RF probes in nominal zero air-gap and increased air-gap configurations (by interposition of Kapton layers). The tested units show an unaltered frequency response with additional 200-300 μm air-gap under DC bias currents of 100 A. Distortion by-products are measured after cleaning the signal generator with a high-order low-pass filter and found negligible and at the limit of the used instrumentation.

Keywords—current probe, electromagnetic compatibility, non-linearity, saturation, test fixture.

I. INTRODUCTION

The many distorting loads and complex grid arrangements necessitate more than ever of extensive measurements of conducted emissions (CE) and grid impedance (GI), to prevent excessive distortion and resonance phenomena and to evaluate possible mitigations [1]. Measurements may be carried out in frequency or time domain with a common important element, the toroidal radio-frequency (RF) current probe, possibly of the clamp-on type to minimize the impact on existing installations. This device turns out useful also as the main element of a galvanically insulated voltage probe for the measurement of grid voltage [2] with realizations working up to 30 MHz [3]. The major problem of such devices for their use in live conditions is tolerating large and variable loading conditions, that translate in large current intensity that might drive the probe into saturation [4]. An alternative is using air-core probes like Rogowski ones, with of course worse accuracy and a more limited frequency range.

RF current probes are transformer based, with multiple secondary turns around a ferrite core placed around the conductor under measurement, that represents the 1-turn primary winding [5]. In general, for RF probes with an output impedance of $50\ \Omega$ the total impedance presented to the internal winding is $25\ \Omega$ and the number of turns can be estimated by comparing with the declared transfer impedance Z_t in the center band: for Z_t values ranging between $10\ \text{dB}\Omega$ and $16\ \text{dB}\Omega$, the internal number of secondary turns may be estimated as ranging between 8 and 4 [6].

Ferrite materials are designed and selected for a large saturation point, using in addition solutions like distributed air-gap. It is commonplace that DC or AC current intensity in excess of a hundred Amperes may cause concern for distortion byproducts caused by non-linearity and eventually

saturation. Besides the generation of harmonic components, another undesirable effect is the compression of the secondary current due to the decreased magnetic permeability. Whereas both phenomena are relevant for CE measurements, it is nevertheless true that harmonic byproducts are irrelevant in a scenario of grid impedance measurement using one single frequency at a time (swept or stepped sine test). Also in the case of bulk current injection probes the study of non-linearity has been limited to the case of increased insertion loss (or compression) [7].

It is observed that many RF probes on the market bear a simple indication of the maximum tolerated primary current without clarification of the adopted criterion (namely the amount of non-linearity or compression that is deemed tolerable) [8], [9]. It is possibly related to the 1dB measurement error cited in the CISPR 16-1-2, sec. 5.1 [10].

For this reason analyzing the non-linear behavior of such probes discussing an affordable test setup to verify saturation is of some importance and helps determining the tradeoff between intensity of the primary current and consequent distortion. The work aims among other things at quantifying the benefit of additional air-gap, implemented by means of Kapton adhesive tape layers of known thickness at the accessible surfaces with the open probe. The setup is described in Sec. II and results of frequency response and distortion under biased conditions are provided in Sec. III.

II. PROBLEM DEFINITION AND SETUP

A. Problem definition

The problem is on the one hand the evaluation of DC or AC bias on the linearity characteristics of the RF probe (distortion by-products and frequency response compression), and on the hand the investigation of possible corrections by increasing the probe air-gap (that is applicable even on commercially available products and does not require a special design).

Non-linearity is evaluated with a standard method feeding the test fixture with a low-distortion sine signal (from a waveform generator, WG) and measuring the resulting spectrum at the harmonic frequencies with a spectrum analyzer (SA). The WG purity was improved by applying a low-pass filter (LPF) designed and built for the test, in order to extend the spurious free dynamic range to detect small non-linearity byproducts.

The frequency response is measured using a VNA and this is repeated for the various tested air-gap thickness values.

Fig. 1. Picture of the setup consisting of the test fixture, the RF probe and the additional winding.

On top of this there is the effect of large-intensity DC or AC grid currents, that is investigated for an affordable method that allows application of up to some hundreds Ampère-turns without interfering with the probe operation.

B. Description of setup

An openable (clamp-on) RF probe is considered that allows to access its internal air-gap surfaces of the two split ferrite halves. The output of the RF probe is terminated on the matched 50Ω impedance of the measuring SA (or data acquisition system), whereas the primary conductor is represented by the test fixture with the inclusion of an additional winding to inject a separate DC or low-frequency AC current. Due to mechanical constraints the number of turns is $N_t = 26$ spanning the available 30 mm on the quarter of the internal circumference. Details are visible in Fig. 1.

The selected RF probes are a Tekbox mod. TBCP5-150k400 with the winding and test fixture and a Tekbox mod. TBCP2-250 [11], that allows more space for the winding having a larger bore. The TBCP2 is a commercial product and features a nominal transfer impedance $Z_t = 13\text{ dB}\Omega$ and a maximum primary current I_1 of 80 A. Its -3 dB bandwidth is 0.230 MHz to 350 MHz and it is usable with reduced Z_t values down to include the supraharmonic range, so 2 kHz; the Z_t degradation is linear as 20 dB/dec.

The used test fixture was conceived for the TBCP5, that remains perfectly centered thanks to the two nylon circular sleeves. The TBCP2, instead, is kept centered with foam spacers. As for the length in the longitudinal direction, the TBCP2 is smaller and thus one may wonder if this alters the test fixture response [12]. In reality, the explored frequency range is limited to 30 MHz, at which the test fixture calibration area is still electrically short. This is confirmed by [12], Fig. 6, where up to 30 MHz the observed variability is less than 2%. It is well noted in [13] that nothing can be done when the longitudinal size of the probe is comparable to the wavelength, leading to an additional uncertainty of $\pm 3\text{ dB}$.

C. Application of the low-frequency saturating current

The objective is to evaluate the probe non-linearity and saturation when undergoing a superposed DC or AC bias current: this may be carried out by means of an additional winding, or by direct injection.

As we will see, the use of such winding causes issues of coupling to the probe itself by modifying its response. It is clear that such a winding couples magnetically with the probe, resulting in a 3-winding magnetic circuit: the center line of the test fixture, the RF probe and the additional bias winding. In short-circuit conditions such winding behaves like a short-circuit loop, causing two negative effects: reducing the probe output by its loading effect and increased resonance problems. Keeping such winding in open-circuit conditions minimizes the inductive coupling, that results relevant only when self-resonance with the own parasitic capacitance occurs. A quasi-open-circuit condition may be simulated by feeding with large-value inductors, like those of a bias-tee device. Resonance effects may be further reduced by providing distributed loading by inserting resistors between adjacent turns (not done in the present case, as it would require a significant modification and a thorough preliminary study to optimize values and positioning along the winding).

This external influence may be avoided removing the external winding and using direct injection. Discarding for obvious reasons the injection of the full primary current through the test fixture, a scaled-down DC or AC bias current may be injected into the the RF probe N connector, by means e.g. of a bias-tee circuit.

What is not obvious is the correspondence between the injected bias current at the secondary $I_{2,LF}$ with the primary current that is instead related to the application in a power system. Relying on a simple equivalent circuit, we may say that the secondary voltage drop on the assumed $Z_2 = 50\Omega$ output impedance must be the same resulting from the application of the primary current through the Z_t impedance. This calculation is possible at e.g. 50 Hz, but not at DC, where there is no induction effect and thus no inductive transfer. Considering a low-frequency AC injected bias with $f_{LF} = 50\text{ Hz}$, the equivalency for the secondary bias current $I_{2,LF}$ through the RF probe operation is approximately:

$$k_{LF} = \frac{I_{2,LF}}{I_{1,LF}} = \frac{Z_t(f_{LF})}{Z_2} \quad (1)$$

The proportionality must be verified by applying a 50 Hz test primary current and measuring the resulting secondary voltage $V_{2,LF}$.

D. Instrumentation

As with all distortion measurements on particularly linear devices, care must be taken to provide a clean undistorted test signal: presently a synthesized WG with a spurious free dynamic range of about 70 dB is being used to collect the first results. The amplitude of the output signal was originally kept under 100 mVpk, so to reduce distortion by-products. After the

LPF introduction, the signal has increased up to 500 mVpp, in order to improve the dynamic range with respect to the noise floor. Considering that the performance of the RF probe should be evaluated with a margin of at least 10 dB, a cautious requirement for the LPF to connect at the WG output is of attenuating by 30 dB to 40 dB the second harmonic, amounting thus to a 5-7th-order filter.

The designed filter is a Chebyshev 9th order passive filter (see the complete PCB in Fig. 3) that matches input and output impedance quite well and provides attenuation of the 2nd harmonic of about -66 dB compared to the fundamental, as shown in Fig. 4. It is remarked that the designed -3 dB cutoff frequency with standard $11 \mu\text{H}$, $13.3 \mu\text{H}$, 2.7nF and 5.6nF at 1 MHz moves from a clean -3 dB to -3.28 dB once DC resistance and high-frequency losses in the employed inductors are included.

It is worth mentioning also that the Chebyshev filter was designed for good impedance matching up to 1 MHz simply by selecting 1.12 MHz as the cutoff frequency during the design, giving up some dB of attenuation. It is known, in fact, that input impedance deteriorates right at the transition over the cutoff frequency. Also the calculated values of inductors and capacitors were manually adjusted to match the most commonly available values, with some trial and error. The resulting impedance at 1 MHz is 51.85Ω with a reflection coefficient of 0.018. The designed match at 0.9 MHz to 0.92 MHz is perfect at 50Ω within $\pm 0.1 \Omega$.

A similar behavior occurs for the 100 kHz test frequency, having designed the Chebyshev filter with 10x larger components (so $110 \mu\text{H}$, $133 \mu\text{H}$, 27nF and 56nF), again manually adjusted to commercially available values, and featuring slightly lower longitudinal resistance due to the almost non-existent inductor losses. In general only for the 10 MHz version the influence of losses is relevant on the longitudinal resistance that is otherwise dominated by the DC resistance of the inductors.

The SA and vector network analyzer (VNA) have no particular characteristics. For completeness of information:

- The SA is an Anritsu mod. MS2036C [14], with input-related spur as low as -60 dBc (so 10^{-6}) with a floor of residual spur of -90 dBm ; assuming a fundamental at about -10 dBm (accounting for the WG output level and attenuation through the Chebyshev filter), there is room for 6 decades of spurious free dynamic range, where any distortion introduced by the RF probe may be spotted out; the Chebyshev filter, in fact, adds 3-4 decades of attenuation to the most relevant low-order harmonics.
- The VNA used for measuring the frequency response is the Tekbox mod. TBVNA-6000 [15], operating over the 1 Hz to 6 GHz frequency interval with typical output signal amplitude accuracy of $\pm 1 \text{ dB}$ and an input return loss better than -20 dB up to 1.5 GHz.
- The VNA used for the Chebyshev LPF characterization is the same Anritsu mod. MS2036C above with a 5 kHz $- 6 \text{ GHz}$ frequency range, S_{21} transmission magnitude

Fig. 2. Picture of the application of Kapton film in the TBCP5 air-gap.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4. Frequency response of the 9th order Chebyshev filter for the 1 MHz version: (a) simulated with Simulink, including inductors' DC resistance (nominal value as per datasheets) and losses (estimated from the specification of the inductors Q factor and resonance frequency); (b) measured with VNA calibrated with full 2-port SOLT (S_{21} blue, S_{11} orange, S_{22} green). To note the slight deformation at 2 MHz due to possibly inaccurate cancellation of bias-tee influence, as the setup temperature changed.

frequency; the reduction is proportional to the air-gap thickness as an overall decrease of 20 dB is observed for a tenfold increase of the thickness. A Z_t value of about $4.4\ \Omega$ is maintained over the flat portion of the frequency response for all air-gap thickness values.

The winding was then supplied with DC bias current keeping an open condition by means of the Tekbox mod. TBBT01 bias-tee [16] (that has a low-frequency inductance of 5 mH). Some sample tests are shown below in Fig. 6 for a total 100 A_{dc} biasing current and two different air-gap values.

The behavior of the probe under test is quite good already with 200 μm of air-gap and 300 μm make the two frequency responses (under 0 A bias and 100 A bias) almost indistinguishable, as shown in Fig. 6. This implies a much better performance in terms of maximum current in the sense of the 1 dB measurement error criterion.

The weird profile above about 5 MHz is due to the influence of the external winding and its multiple resonances, decoupled, but not completely, by inserting a low-frequency (≥ 5 kHz) high-current (≤ 10 A) bias-tee (TBBT01).

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5. TBCP5 frequency response: (a) nominal (as per datasheet) and (b) with increasing air-gap thickness (from 50 μm to 600 μm of Kapton).

B. Non-linear by-products

A series of tests has been carried out at different frequencies, to check the linearity characteristics under increasing bias. The results were originally obtained by correction of the measured probe output distortion V_p by the distortion that characterizes the signal generator output V_g , having selected a 100 mV_{pk} output level as a compromise between current intensity through the probe and signal distortion. After the LPF introduction the WG signal was increased, while still providing a clean signal with spurious free dynamic range better than 120 dB.

The test has been carried out at 1 MHz, by measuring then the first 9 harmonics, setting the spectrum analyzer (SA) to each harmonic (2 MHz ... 9 MHz) and a small span of 50 Hz. An adequately low resolution bandwidth (RBW = 1 Hz) was set to reduce the noise floor and achieve the desired sweep time and frequency resolution, smaller than the adopted RBW. In this way the SA dynamic range may be improved down to 40 dB μV and the SA pre-amplifier can be switched on to reduce the noise floor (by about 10 dB), being limited by the input attenuation set to 10 dB, in order to guarantee some protection and a suitable VSWR reduction. In addition, the use of the pre-amplifier reduces the input-related spur of the SA itself, that is declared at -70 dBc, right for a -30 dBm input

(a)

(b)

Fig. 6. Preliminary results of the TBCP5 frequency response under 0 and 100 A with air-gap of (a) 200 μm and (b) 300 μm .

that is centered between the two WG output signal amplitudes of 100 mV_{pp} (power of the probe output of about -37 dBm) and 500 mV_{pp} (about -23 dBm).

The noise floor of the SA itself is negligible, as declared by the manufacturer around -160 dBm, with the same settings used presently for these tests: RMS detection, reference level at -57 dBm, “performance” sweep mode (chosen for a matter of acceptable speed of measurement). The major noise contribution is from the WG through the filter and from the environment, in the order of -15 dB μV , or -120 dBm, at $\text{RBW} = 1$ Hz.

The results are shown in Table 1 for a test carried out at 1 MHz, where the fundamental and all relevant harmonics lie in the flat part of the frequency response). The current flowing in the test fixture and TBCP5 is directly derived from the WG output level of 500 mV_{pp} and passing through the Chebyshev LPF. As a note the filter is designed using inductors with a minimum tolerable current of 150 mA_{pk}, at which the largest inductors of the 100 kHz channel approach the 10% inductance variation limit indicated by the manufacturer. For the 1 MHz channel the limit is around 350 mA_{pk}.

The overall behavior of the TBCP5 probe is quite good with the first harmonic components barely recognizable above the SA noise floor. The measurement at each harmonic frequency was carried out by averaging ten sweeps, that flattens

Table 1. Estimate of distortion components at 75 Adc.

Test frequency and harmonics	Dist. (dBc) no bias	Dist. (dBc) 75 A bias
2 MHz	< -102	-98.2
3 MHz	< -102	-100.5
≥ 4 MHz	—	—

slightly the noise floor, although the commented -20 dB μV represents the present limitation as the RBW cannot be decreased further. The estimate of the relative amplitude of each harmonic is done by using the separately measured fundamental amplitude at the output of the probe V_1 , as fed through the test fixture and the Chebyshev LPF with 500 mV_{pp}: $V_1 = 81.7$ dB μV . This gives a dynamic range down to the noise floor of about 102 dB.

The measured distortion components are all at or below the noise floor, except for the first two (at 2 MHz and 3 MHz) that become visible when a total of 75 Adc are applied (calculated from the measured 2.95 Adc of input current to the bias winding). The result is indicated in Table 1, where, however, an accurate estimate of the deterioration caused by the applied bias is not possible as the distortion without bias applied is not measurable in the present conditions. Two comments on the accuracy of the exposed results need to be done: first, such low harmonic amplitude is estimate without correction for the noise floor and its dispersion, as adjacent bins may vary by several dB; second, common-mode coupling is possible at such low amplitudes, as grounding and ground reference needs still to be optimized by evaluating its influence on the results and the SA is floating.

IV. CONCLUSION

RF current probes are an important element for the measurement of conducted emissions and impedance in modern grids and power networks, featuring a significant level of distortion. Due to the variable grid impedance conditions, equipment such as power converters benefit from on site measurements, rather than limiting to laboratory ones.

Under real conditions the current intensity at the fundamental may be quite large, bringing the RF probe in a non-linear region of operation. From this the exigency of characterizing such probes under large low-frequency current intensity in order to derive two main characteristics: the frequency response evaluating any reduction of their transfer impedance due to the approaching saturation condition and distortion by-products due to internal non-linearity.

Usual test fixtures are not suitable for the direct application of the low-frequency current intensity of interest (in excess of a hundred A), so that an external winding is proposed, studying its influence on the RF probe itself. Alternatively, a direct injection of the saturation signal into the RF probe connector could be a viable solution.

The saturation tests have been carried out on a Tekbox probe mod. TBCP5-150k400 investigating the effect of an

additional air-gap created by applying multiple layers of Kapton tape of known thickness. The effect is the shift of the corner frequency and a reduction of the coupling, and of the transfer impedance, at low frequency. Using a gap of 200 μm to 300 μm it was shown that the frequency response is unaltered up to 100 A for a probe that has a nominal saturation point of 80 A. At the cost of repeating the probe calibration, applying additional air-gap on occasion of high-current intensity tests reveals to be viable and economic. In fact a cheaper probe model may be chosen, featuring a higher Z_t at the expense of a reduced saturation current, applying the additional air gap when needed.

The distortion components were initially tested by subtracting the generator distortion from the measured values. The WG output is cleaned using a high-order LPF (a passive 9th order Chebyshev filter tuned to the three test frequencies of 100 kHz, 1 MHz and 10 MHz) in 3 separate channels. The consequential attenuation of the 2nd harmonic is more than 60 dB, so improving generator's performance by three orders of magnitude. The RF probe distortion was estimated then by neglecting the incoming distortion (after the Chebyshev filter) replying on a direct measurement of the spectrum at the probe output connector.

The increase of the saturation threshold by applying the said air-gap, and consequential improvement of distortion performance, does not deteriorate other probe characteristics, as listed in sec. 5.1 and Annex B of CISPR 16-1-2 [10]:

- the prescribed flat response is preserved, as shown in Fig. 5;
- the 1 dB amplitude compression criterion is fulfilled although the discussion at the end has focused on distortion by-products;
- susceptibility to external electric field and capacitive coupling to the primary conductor is negligible, as long as the internal winding is shielded, at least by the external enclosure.

Further development and analysis is necessary mostly in two directions:

- improvement of the setup for the SA dynamic range and verification of grounding and common-mode coupling;
- modeling of the internal circuit with the possibility of bias direct injection at the probe output, rather than using the external additional winding, removing its influence from the high-frequency probe response and the need for expensive and bulky bias-tee.

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REFERENCES

- [1] A. Mariscotti, L. Sandrolini, and G. Pasini, "Variability caused by setup and operating conditions for conducted EMI of switched mode power supplies over the 2–1000 kHz interval," *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 71, pp. 1–9, 2022, ISSN: 1557-9662. DOI: 10.1109/tim.2022.3162291.
- [2] I. Fernandez, M. Alberro, J. Montalban, A. Arrinda, I. Angulo, and D. de la Vega, "A new voltage probe with improved performance at the 10 kHz – 500 kHz frequency range for field measurements in LV networks," *Measurement*, vol. 145, pp. 519–524, Oct. 2019, ISSN: 0263-2241. DOI: 10.1016/j.measurement.2019.05.106.
- [3] A. Mariscotti, "Design and experimental verification of an isolated voltage probe for the 2 kHz – 30 MHz interval operating in live conditions," *Measurement*, 2025.
- [4] S. Büyük, A. Mariscotti, K. Štibernik, O. Şen, and M. Wojciechowski, "A portable VNA-based system for grid impedance measurements," in *2024 International Symposium on Electromagnetic Compatibility – EMC Europe*, IEEE, Sep. 2024, pp. 464–469. DOI: 10.1109/emceurop e59828.2024.10722179.
- [5] C. Carobbi and L. Millanta, "Circuit loading in radio-frequency current measurements: The insertion impedance of the transformer probes," *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 59, no. 1, pp. 200–204, Jan. 2010, ISSN: 1557-9662. DOI: 10.1109/tim.2009.2022450.
- [6] D. Zaikin, "Model of the Rohde & Schwarz EZ-17 current probe and creation of a DIY analog for EMI study," Feb. 2022. DOI: 10.36227/tehrxiv.19199660.v1.
- [7] F. Grassi, C. Rostamzadeh, P. Kolbe, G. Spadacini, and S. A. Pignari, "Assessing linearity of injection probes used in BCI test setups for automotive applications," in *IEEE International Symposium on Electromagnetic Compatibility*, IEEE, Aug. 2013, pp. 128–133. DOI: 10.1109/isemc.2013.6670395.
- [8] Fischer Custom Communications, *Current monitor probes*, <https://www.fischercc.com/type/current-monitor-probes/> (available online, last accessed on 03-05-2025), 2020.
- [9] Com-Power, *Emissions current probes*, <https://www.com-power.com/products/current-probes/emissions-current-probes> (available online, last accessed on 03-05-2025), 2022.
- [10] CISPR 16-1-2, *Specification for radio disturbance and immunity measuring apparatus and methods — Part 1-2: Radio disturbance and immunity measuring apparatus –coupling devices for conducted disturbance measurements*, IEC, Geneva, Switzerland, 2017.
- [11] TekBox Digital Solutions, *TBCP2 32 mm snap on RF current monitoring probes (TBCP2-250)*, https://www.tekbox.com/product/TBCP2_250_Manual.pdf, 2024.
- [12] A. Ruddle, "Calibration of current measurement transducers in oversized calibration fixtures," *IEEE Transactions on Electromagnetic Compatibility*, vol. 47, no. 1, pp. 196–201, Feb. 2005, ISSN: 0018-9375. DOI: 10.1109/temc.2004.838227.
- [13] D. Pommerenke, R. Chundru, and S. Chandra, "A new test setup and method for the calibration of current clamps," *IEEE Transactions on Electromagnetic Compatibility*, vol. 47, no. 2, pp. 335–343, May 2005, ISSN: 0018-9375. DOI: 10.1109/temc.2005.847381.
- [14] Anritsu MS2036C, *Technical datasheet, 11410-00548, rev. AW*, <https://dl.cdn-anritsu.com/en-us/test-measurement/files/Brochures-Datasheet-Catalogs/datasheet/11410-00548AW.pdf>, 2024.
- [15] Tekbox, *TBVNA-6000: 1 Hz – 6 GHz vector network analyzer*, <https://www.tekbox.com/product/tbvna-6000-1-hz-6-ghz-vector-network-analyzer/> (available online, last accessed on 28-05-2025), 2025.
- [16] Tekbox, *TBTT01: High-current bias tee*, <https://www.tekbox.com/product/tbtt01-high-current-bias-tee/> (available online, last accessed on 28-05-2025), 2025.